

Performance Evaluation of Life Insurance Corporation of India for the past decade: Bibliography of Unclassified Literature

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ABSTRACT

The insurance sector has a long history in India. The insurance sector in India has come a full circle from being an open competitive market to nationalization and back to a liberalized market again. Tracing the developments in the Indian insurance sector reveals the 360-degree turn witnessed over a period of almost 190 years.

The business of life insurance in India in its existing form started in India in the year 1818 with the establishment of the Oriental Life Insurance Company in Calcutta. The 1st legal enactment was made in 1870. The 1st Indian Insurance Act was passed in 1938 and amended in 1950, when it was nationalized. However, the sector was once again thrown open to the private sector on December 1999, followed by the establishment of the Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (IRDA) in April 2000.

Due to its importance, especially for the poor and salaried, as a medium of risk cover, savings and tax relief, the performance of LIC of India has to be monitored closely at regular intervals. The present paper attempts to prepare a bibliography of unclassified literature on this aspect.

It is observed from the study of different research works that though the development of distribution is a true trend within the industry, very few studies have concentrated on the same. Some of the studies together with their area of research are enlisted in the presentation.

Keywords: Insurance, Performance, Bibliography over the past decade.

INTRODUCTION

Since inception the Indian life insurance industry has its own origin and history. It has passed through many hurdles and hindrances in order to attain the present status. However, the income earning capacity of an individual citizen of a nation and the eagerness and awareness of the general public are the two key determinants of the growth of any insurance industry. In the Indian context, the insurance habits among the general public during the independence decade was rare and in the following decades, it has slowly increased. There was a remarkable improvement in the Indian insurance industry soon after the economic reform era (1991). After 1991 the Indian life insurance industry has geared up in all respects, as well as it is being forced to face a lot of healthy competition from many national as well as international private insurance players. The study reveals that there is a tremendous growth in the performance of Indian Life Insurance industry and LIC due to the policy of LPG. Insurance industry also improved a lot due to the emergence of Private sector and opening up for foreign players. Further there is also a huge change in the investment pattern of LIC. There is a increasing trend toward the investment in Stock market by

LIC from 60% to 93% from 1980 to 2009 due to the effective regulation of SEBI and increasing transparency of stock market.

In one form or another, we all own insurance. Whether it's auto, medical, liability, disability or life, insurance serves as an excellent risk-management and wealth-preservation tool. Having the right kind of insurance is a critical component of any good financial plan. While most of us own insurance, many of us don't understand what it is or how it works.

Insurance is appropriate when you want to protect against a significant monetary loss. Take life insurance as an example. If you are the primary breadwinner in your home, the loss of income that your family would experience as a result of our premature death is considered a significant loss and hardship that you should protect them against. It would be very difficult for your family to replace your income, so the monthly premiums ensure that if you die, your income will be replaced by the insured amount. The same principle applies to many other forms of insurance. If the potential loss will have a detrimental effect on the person or entity, insurance makes sense. Today, life insurance is used for many reasons, including wealth preservation and estate tax planning.

Life insurance provides you with the opportunity to protect yourself and your family from personal risk exposures like repayment of debts after death, providing for a surviving spouse and children, fulfilling other economic goals (such as putting your kids through college), leaving a charitable legacy, paying for funeral expenses, etc. Life insurance protection is also important if you are a business owner or a key person in someone else's business, where your death (or your partner's death) might wreak financial havoc. Life insurance is a great financial planning tool, but should never be thought of as a savings vehicle. In general, there are often far better places to hold and grow your money as you get older.

Insurance is an integral part of any personal financial plan. The type of insurance and the amount of coverage you obtain all depends on your unique financial and family circumstances, and must be evaluated carefully. When considering purchasing coverage, you should review all the potential risks and the financial impact of these risks on your financial health. This will help you determine what options to look for and what questions to ask. What you need to keep in mind is that you do not want to be underinsured or overinsured, which means you have to do your homework before you buy. And as with any type of financial product, you must read the fine print and consult with a competent advisor.

Life insurance management, as a distinct discipline, has been playing prominent role and gaining ground slowly and firmly in the present day post-liberalization scenario. The breakthrough achievements can come only from the untiring, sincere and diligent efforts of all the stakeholders.

The major change of the life insurance industry in India is the opening up to private and global players. With this, the monopolistic character of the public sector giant i.e. LIC of India, has been replaced by competition subject to the regulatory conditions of the IRDA. Insurance has become a matter of persuasion rather than solicitation. The customer can choose now among industry players, schemes available, nature and types of risks and also the costs involved therein.

An enquiry into the nature and factors responsible for performance of the LIC of India and also the private sector insurance players during the period 2000-01 to 2009-10

will be helpful in formulating the future course of action in the area of product innovation and development, asset-liability management and customer relationship management of the life insurance players in India.

This will enable the Government, IRDA, LIC of India, private sector players, employees, insurance marketers and the policyholders to know the causes underlying the existing position, to understand and appreciate the other stakeholders' attitude and to promote compromising and conciliatory behaviour which is the essential prerequisite for the healthy growth of life insurance industry in our country. It is hoped that this study will be useful in the context of the imperative need for toning up the efficiency of the working of both the public and private sector units, which are expected to play a crucial role in the years to come and give a new outlook to the life insurance policy laid down by the Government and the IRDA.

Its aim is also to find out why certain deficiencies have occurred and how they can be avoided. It requires naturally a lot of objective assessment of the problems with the application of statistical techniques. It will also be useful to bring to light many aspects, with broader perspective, of the performance evaluation of the life insurance industry that contribute for higher insurance penetration and better customer service are brought to light.

In order to find out the gaps in research, the literature already available pertaining to the problem is to be reviewed. The literature on life insurance industry in India includes books, compendia, theses, dissertations, study reports and articles published by academicians and researchers in different periodicals. The review of this literature gives an idea to concentrate on the unexplored area.

Objective of the Study: To present the review of literature for the past decade.

Bibliography of Unclassified Literature

DR.K.V.Ramanathan,¹ in "A Study On The Cost Control Efficiency Of Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) Of India, observes that : The cost is an important element to determine the profit of any product or service. There is a positive relation between cost and profit. Cost control is a prime objective of each and every business and to control the cost of operations and for that different kinds of strategies are adopted by them. In insurance business the expenses are incurred in several heads like, product (policy) innovation, marketing of products (advertising & sales promotion), underwriting commission, and agency commission etc. The Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) of India is taking enormous efforts in the Introduction of new products and expansion of business and incurring huge expenditures regarding this process. However, these expenditures are inevitable and reasonable one. This article is trying evaluating the cost control efficiency of LIC during the period between 2002 to 2012 (10 years). The required and relevant data have been collected through the annual reports of LIC and put under analysis. The analysis revealed that, in the first two years during the study period, LIC did not reduce its expenses, but in the last year and subsequent three years from 2007 to 2010, LIC retrenched its expenditure as a measure of contingency. They employed various strategies to keep the expenses based on their income. It is clear from the insignificant covariance of income and expenses. LIC in the first seven years spent more of its income to salaries of the employees to get their co-operations. But in the last two years, the measure of contingency made

LIC to be careful enough to deal with the salaries of employees. The present study involves calculation of cost efficiency score of life insurance sector in India with the use of Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA). Life Insurance Corporation of India has consistently secured a cost efficiency score of 1 in all the years from 2000-01 to 2011-12 and scored the highest rank for all the years under study. Thus Life Insurance Corporation of India has consistently been a cost efficient organization. While in the case of the private life insurance companies, the cost efficiency score has been inconsistent.

According to **Mohd. Yameen, Nikita Kumari**² the contribution of insurance sector in any economy is of the crucial importance. Insurance plays a very crucial role in reducing the strain on national economy and helping it to grow directly and indirectly. Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) is the main public sector insurance company of India. The present study is an attempt to evaluate the financial soundness of Life Insurance Company of India.

The performance of LIC has been checked through two ratios namely; Capital Adequacy and Earning and Profitability. For the purpose of statistical interpretation of data, the researcher has also used Chi square test. The result of study concluded that capital adequacy, Earning, and profitability is not encouraging over the study period from 2001-02 to 2012-13. LIC requires to strengthen its capital base and improve its performance.

Gowd T. Narayana, Kiran C. Bhanu, Dr. Rao Ch. Ramaprasada³ made an attempt on the current status, growth, volume of competition and SWOT analysis of the Life Insurance Industry, to analyze the overall performance of Life Insurance Industry of India between pre and post reform era and to measure the effectiveness of investment strategy of LIC of India during the period 1998 to 2010-11. The collected data were analyzed by using Coefficient of Variation, student t test and ANOVA. The study reveals that there is tremendous growth in the performance of Life Insurance Industry and LIC due to the policy of LPG. More over Insurance Industry improved a lot due to the emergence of private sector and allowing foreign players. There is huge change in the investment strategy of LIC. Private sector performance in terms of total premium earned, number of policies issued and market share is in increasing trend where as LIC market share is in declining trend except in total premium earned and total policies issued. LIC's investment towards stock market instruments is in increasing trend. The investment of LIC increased from 77.5% in 1998 to 95.81% in 2010-11 due to effective regulation of SEBI and increasing transparency and performance of Indian corporate securities.

Arnika Srivastava, Sarika Tripathi and Amit Kumar,⁴ expressed that the Insurance industry contributes to the financial sector of an economy and also provides an important social security net in developing countries. The growth of the insurance sector in India has been phenomenal. The insurance industry has undergone a massive change over the last few years and the metamorphosis has been noteworthy. There are numerous private and government insurance companies in India that have become synonymous with the term insurance over the years. Offering a diversified product portfolio and excellent services the many insurance companies in India have managed to make their way into almost every Indian household.

Yogita Sharma⁵ opined that there is hardly a facet of the Indian psyche that the concept of 'foreign' has not permeated. This term, connoting modernization,

international brands and acquisitions by MNCs in popular imagination, has acquired renewed significance after the reforms initiated by the Indian Government in 1991. Generally speaking FDI refers to capital inflows from abroad that invest in the production capacity of the economy and are “usually preferred over other forms of external finance because they are non-debt creating, non-volatile and their returns depend on the performance of the projects financed by the investors. FDI also facilitates international trade and transfer of knowledge, skills and technology. “Foreign direct investment is of growing importance to global economic growth. This Paper mainly focus on the Foreign Direct Investment in the Insurance sector and its significance in insurance sector in India . The Insurance sector in India has a great potential even during the downtrend and FDI flow is expected to rise in the near future. This paper attempts on the current status of FDI in insurance sector in India. Currently, only 26% of FDI is permitted in insurance sector. The total insurance business would touch US\$ 60 billion size. If insurance sector is opened up to an extent of 49% for FDI, it is expected that FDI’s contribution to insurance business would touch nearly US\$ 2 billion.

Sandeep Bakhshi⁶ writes that the reporting standards are essentially principles-based and as such, it is for the industry participants to demonstrate sufficient maturity to ensure that the regime is eventually successful. The standards seek to differentiate between contracts that can be separated into distinct insurance and investment components and those that cannot be separated

Murali⁷ states that there are some strange insurance products in the global insurance market beyond the routine covers that one has got to see more regularly. Such insurance covers that make an insured to look into are celebrity body parts insurance, moustache insurance, prize payout insurance, horse breeding insurance, casino insurance, lottery winnings insurance, virgins against pregnancy insurance, judge insurance and paternity insurance.

Baradhwaj⁸ contends that insurers need not look far for implementing the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Philosophy but adopt simple practices of serving the clientele effectively and demonstrate their zeal to improve the overall standards of life. CSR is the deliberate inclusion of public interest into corporate decision-making and the honouring of a triple bottom line: people, planet and profit.

Sonal Nena⁹ expressed that Insurance industries in India now a day have taken a giant shape especially after privatization and introduction of Insurance Regulatory & Development Authority (IRDA). Life Insurance Corporation of India is one of the most significant public sector which plays excellent job in selling its products. But since last few years it is facing tremendous competition as many private players have emerged. The idea behind this study therefore to know the growth and performance of LIC. The researcher is going to analyze the major source of income (Premium Earned) of the sampled unit, as well as the significant heads of expenses of LIC to measure the performance during the period of the study.

Ms. Prarthana Shahi¹⁰ comprehensive study was to know whether the implemented strategies have truly helped LIC of India in the changing trends of the society and will also suggest how these recent trends have helped LIC of India as a whole to manage the existing leading position in the life insurance market.

KPMG¹¹ has presented a series of papers which form part of this report entitled ‘Insurance Industry – Road Ahead’ which is an attempt to understand and

discuss the various issues that the Indian insurance industry is dealing with, and to bring to the fore emerging trends that will shape the growth and profitability of the industry in the near to medium term future. One of the papers focuses on the challenges and opportunities in micro insurance, where the development of products and operating models by the insurance companies addressing the needs of the micro insurance sector requires strong support from the government and the regulator

Chavare¹² presented an abstract in the form of the concluding statement that provides the quick review of the paper. This abstract is helpful to make aware the readers about the subject under study. In this paper researcher has attempted to provide detailed information regarding Brand Loyalty with respect to Life Insurance Corporation of India. The paper titled "A Study Of Brand Loyalty", with Reference To, "Life Insurance Corporation Of India". At present, investment of saving has assumed great importance. According to the study of the market, it is being observed that markets are being doing well in Insurance. In near Future a proper financial planning is required to invest money in all type of financial project because there is good potential in market to invest. In this paper great emphasis is given in understanding the perception of investors towards the brand. The main objective of this project is to know various determinants of brand loyalty. The researcher has drawn certain conclusions, which are based on the analyzed data. In addition researcher has made an attempt to suggest some remedies to improve grey areas of the services of organization. After analyzing the feedback the conclusion has been made that the respondent are very loyal towards brand LIC.

According to **Liji Panda & Bimal Chandra Mishra**,¹³ an investment refers to the commitment of funds at present, in anticipation of some positive rate of return in future. Today the spectrum of investment is indeed wide. An investment is confronted with array of investment avenues. Among all investment, investment in equity is in best high proportion. This is because the history of stock market is booming and bursts overnight millionaires, an instant pauper. Indian economy is doing indeed well in recent years. The study has been undertaken to analyze the investment pattern of LIC of India. The main reasons behind the study are the factors like income, economy condition, and the risk covering nature of the investment.

Vikas Gautam and Mukund Kumar¹⁴ presented an attempt to illustrate the attitudes of Indian consumers towards the insurance services. The study has been made by collecting the responses of consumers through structured questionnaire on five point Likert scale. A total 377 responses were collected to assess the level of awareness about the insurance services and their attitude towards insurance services. Findings of the research show that basic socio demographic and economic variables have significant impact on consumers' attitudes towards insurance services in Indian scenario. The findings of the present study may act as input for the insurance companies in Indian market to frame marketing strategies based on socio demographic and economic variables.

Arnika Srivastava, Sarika Tripathi and Amit Kumar,¹⁵ are of the opinion that Insurance industry contributes to the financial sector of an economy and also provides an important social security net in developing countries. The growth of the insurance sector in India has been phenomenal. The insurance industry has undergone a massive change over the last few years and the metamorphosis has been noteworthy. There are numerous private and government insurance companies in India that have become

synonymous with the term insurance over the years. Offering a diversified product portfolio and excellent services the many insurance companies in India have managed to make their way into almost every Indian household.

Hymavathi Kumari¹⁶ presented a research paper aimed at understanding the life insurance sector in India and flagging issues relating to competition in this sector. India's rapid rate of economic growth over the past decade has been one of the more significant developments in the global economy. This growth has its roots in the introduction of economic liberalization in the early 1990s, which has allowed India to exploit its economic potential and raise the population's standard of living. Opening up of the financial sector is one of the financial reforms which the government was to implement as an integral part structural reforms and stabilization process of the economy. Insurance has a very important role in this process. Government allowed the entrance of private players into the industry. As a result, many private insurers also came into existence. At this juncture, an attempt has been made to study the performance of life insurance industry in India in post liberalization era. The study presented analyzes the performance of financial performance of insurance industry both public sector and private sector, its market share, growth have been studied in post liberalization era.

Raji Reddy and Kiran Kumar¹⁷ analysed the past & present status of the Indian insurance sector in general and life insurance in particular. It also discusses about the future of the Indian insurance sector

Rajeev Ahuja Basudeb Guha-Khasnobis¹⁸ submitted a paper which provides an overview of the micro-insurance scene in India and suggests strategies for its further extension. The paper should be useful for all those involved in microfinance.

James¹⁹ emphasizes that risk management for insurer is not merely a one-off sporadic exercise but an on-going management strategy which is at the core of their governance. There is a strategic side to operations that lies at higher corporate levels and is prone to large failures when done wrongly. Strategies are translated into day to day decision-making properly.

Gupta²⁰ has attempted to present a more in-depth analysis on the functional areas of insurance business, design and development of products, management of claims, pricing and marketing of products and the financial operations of insurance companies. It also elaborates the Asset-Liability Management Aspects of the insurance companies

Surya Prakasha Rao and Prasad²¹ emphasized the role played by the public sector insurer, LIC of India, in fulfilling its responsibility towards the society. They considered the Corporation as a model organization and also a front runner in Corporate Social Responsibility.

Mishra and Mishra²² discuss the prospects of insurance companies, privatization of insurance industry, insurance innovation, corporate governance, bancassurance and international insurance. It includes all the latest provisions of insurance legislation beginning from the totally amended Insurance Act, 1993 to IRDA (Protection of Policyholders' Interests) Regulation, 2002. It also deals with the latest development of Insurance in India and abroad along with the possibilities of managing the same amicably and also profitably.

Periasamy,²³ gives a comprehensive view on the privatization of insurance business in India. The background, the ways and the contribution of privatization of life

insurance business to an economy are discussed. The conditions for the success of private insurers are dealt with suitably and also in a comprehensive manner.

Shveta², asserts that the growth in the sale of health insurance policies of the insurers after liberalization of the insurance sector and the increased health-consciousness of our population has virtually changed the face of Indian insurance industry accompanied by some related challenges.

Suresh Kumar²⁵ discusses the important role played by human resources in the LIC of India, a public sector giant, in the Indian insurance market. The monetary evaluation of the importance of this role is also discussed.

Ahuja Alka Harneja Nee Alka²⁶ emphasizes that as an economy is developing, the mindset and emotions of the people are also changing at a rapid pace and the decision to buy an insurance product is mainly affected by the advice of the family members, neighbours, agents and also a desire to save income-tax. Risk coverage and company's brand name are commonly considered the most important factors of the advice.

Mohmed Amin Mir²⁷ discusses the pros and cons of the proposed rise of the cap on FDI in the insurance sector from 26 to 49 percent. He opines that many private insurers welcomed the move as it raises their capital base. This helps maintain adequate solvency margin and bears the escalated initial operation costs low.

Sailender Singh²⁸ focuses on investment management of insurers. He lists out the characteristics of the emerging markets and the constraints faced by LIC in having a profitable and active role.

Vethirajan²⁹ advocates that with so many competitors in insurance industry, it becomes imperative for the insurance players to consider the service to policyholders as their prime objective. They have to settle claims promptly, reduce the management and operating expenses reasonably and introduce novel products that are more practical in nature.

Sarvjeet Kaur³⁰ discusses each and every marketing strategy that reflected different skills and requirements for its success. As such, marketing strategies of the insurance players will necessarily revolve around products, competitive environment and technological factors.

Shendey and Neelkant Rao³¹ finds that the entry of new players has enabled up the spread of life insurance. The monopoly of LIC of India has come to end in insurance sector. Total life insurance premium of an Indian Insurance Industry has increased four-folds since liberalization of insurance industry. LIC has been taking measures to increase its policyholder base through various new schemes like children education, pension plans and constant monitoring of these policies.

Priya Kapoor³² claims that the term plans which are seldom pushed by agents, yet they are the best form of insurance. These are being sold at premiums 40- 50% lower than what they were about 1-2 year ago. Much of this is due to the growing competition in the market.

Shashidharan Kutty,³³ elaborates the qualitative development in the Life Insurance Industry during the last decade, both in the global and also in the Indian context. In his empirical analysis, he finds that the dominant paradigm in sales has been to build the sales infrastructure. Somehow, the growth would automatically materialize and the selling competence will also been enhanced. But, the life insurance, as an industry, is mostly built on trust, protection, preservation and long-term opportunity.

Majumdar³⁴ makes a presentation highlighting therein the buying behavior of life insurance in India, reasons for low penetration and what the insurers can do to raise insurance penetration.

The research by **Gautam and Kumar**³⁵ is an attempt to illustrate the attitudes of Indian consumers towards the insurance services. The study has been made by collecting the responses of consumers through structured questionnaire on five point Likert scale. A total 377 responses were collected to assess the level of awareness about the insurance services and their attitude towards insurance services. Findings of the research show that basic socio demographic and economic variables have significant impact on consumers' attitudes towards insurance services in Indian scenario. The findings of the present study may act as input for the insurance companies in Indian market to frame marketing strategies based on socio demographic and economic variables.

Sandhu and Neetu Bala³⁶ advocate that service quality has become a highly instrumental co-efficient in the aggressive competitive marketing. For success and survival in today's competitive environment, delivering quality service is of paramount importance for any economic enterprise. Life Insurance Corporation of India, the leading insurance company has set up 'benchmarks' in enervating the whole concept of service quality. The present study aims to measure customers' perception towards life insurance service quality. An advocated procedure has been used to develop, refine and validate a scale. Data has been collected from 337 customers from the three cities of Punjab (a progressive State of India). The findings of the study demonstrate that five-factor structure as proposed by Suresh chandar et al. (2001) has been refined to seven-factor construct (consisting of 34 items) representing Proficiency; Media and presentations; Physical and ethical excellence; Service delivery process and purpose; Security and dynamic operations; Credibility; and Functionality. Besides, the study also investigates the relationship between each of the generated service quality dimensions and customers overall evaluation of life insurance service quality. It reveals that among these seven factors, three viz., Proficiency; Physical and ethical excellence; and Functionality have significant impact on the overall service quality of Life Insurance Corporation of India. Managerial implications and directions for further research have also been discussed

Prarthana Shahi³⁷ has extensively surveyed the various aspects relating to the Performance of Life Insurance Corporation of India and other private insurance companies. The suggestions and findings recommended by the researcher will be extremely useful for the life insurance companies to apply and follow in the future.

Selvankumar and Vimal Priyan,³⁸ express that the Growth in Insurance Industry has been spurred by product innovation, vibrant distribution channels coupled with targeted publicity and promotional campaigns by the insurers. Innovations have come not only in the form of the benefits attached to the products but also in the delivery mechanism through various marketing tie-ups within the realm of financial services inside and outside.

Anand Pejawar³⁹ opines that there is an increasing emphasis on prompt customer service and adds that companies have to be imaginative in finding new ways of rendering it. The pre-sale service, though of a different nature, is equally important as the post-sale service unlike other service industry. In case of life insurance, the post-sale service is quite unique and attained more importance due to its long nature/tenure

of the product as it has to run throughout the tenure of the policy. This can range anywhere between 3-5 years to life long i.e. 40-50 years

Rajagopalan Krishnamurthy⁴⁰ reviews the key findings of the India Bancassurance Benchmarking Survey, 2010, a Research Study from Towers Watson. The survey reflects the views of a cross section of insurers and bank intermediaries. Some findings of the Survey are that the average tenure of tie-up with private/foreign banks tended to be longer than the tie-up with the public sector banks. In mature markets, bank distribution agreements have run for an average period of 5 years.

Mishra. and Venugopal⁴¹ discuss at length underwriting basics, philosophy and guidelines of underwriting, sources of underwriting information, physiological systems, technology in underwriting, pricing fundamentals and modern developments and practices in the technology of underwriting. All these aspects are very useful to have an in-depth understanding on insurance underwriting.

Dutta Subit⁴² makes a study of the insurance marketing strategies of the public sector giant after liberalisation in Silchar Division and finds that the customer awareness has improved on insurance products and also the efficiency of marketing of these products by the Corporation is also augmented due to increased competition from private insurance players.

Bishnoi Mahender⁴³ expresses that the prompt settlement of a genuine claim is an important function of the insurance industry and also a foundation for the CRM Strategies. Further, the CRM strategies are proved to help the company to address the important concerns of the customers and also build their patronage continuously. The potential competition in the industry pushed the way of accepting CRM strategies

Ashvin Parekh⁴⁴ stresses the need to train in human resources in order that corporate goals are achieved. He opines that insurance is a difficult product to sell owing to the financial complexity, low financial literacy and lack of awareness among the consumers of the need for such a product. Hence, training modules must be in tune with the organization's vision, mission and strategic objectives.

Ayem Perumal⁴⁵ explains that the business environment for the insurance sector has been fast changing, bringing new opportunities and posing new challenges. He further asserts that the major challenges are market volatility, ever-changing customer needs and structural limitations.

Jawaharlal⁴⁶ in his article under vantage point on "Product Design and Development - Key to Long-Term Success" observes that the designing of new products is dependent on the regulatory environment prevailing in the industry. Looking at the importance of the issue, progressive improvements have been made regularly. The introduction of 'combi-products' is a step in this direction and it is hoped that insurers will make best use of the new initiatives and design consumer-oriented products accordingly.

Sahoo and Das⁴⁷ furnished a comprehensive insight into the basics of risk management and life insurance. The various facets of the IRDA's regulations are also analysed at appropriate places in the book. It also covers the social and rural sector obligations of the insurance companies, role of information technology in insurance marketing and various aspects of competitive environment such as mindset of the consumers, adequacy of capital, market related policies and cost-consciousness.

Pranav Prashad⁴⁸ asserts that several production systems of the rural folk have associated risks which may lead to income and revenue loss and these can be

mitigated only through insurance leading to stabilization of income and reduced poverty. Given the changing eco-systems and improved infrastructure, the need is to look beyond this obligatory requirement and see that the rural sector as a commercial and for profit opportunity for insurers.

Praveen Sanu, Gaurav Jaiswal and Vijay Kumar Panday ⁴⁹ in their article, "A Study of Buying Behaviour of Consumers towards Life Insurance Company", Prestige institute of Management and research, Gwalior, revealed that in present Indian market, the investment habits of Indian consumers are changing very frequently. The individuals have their own perception towards various types of investment plans

Patil, P.B. and Thakkar, P.N. ⁵⁰ article "Impact of Disinvestment on Banking and Insurance Sector" revealed that a strong competition among the insurance companies has led to better services being provided by customer satisfaction can be known from the customer retention ratio. Now most of the companies are customer centric approach, rather than product centric approach which is leading to customer-retention ratio. A study conducted by **Sunayna Khurana** ⁵¹ expressed that the insurance sector plays a very important role in the development of any economy. It is necessary for the economic and overall development of any country.

Pilania Renu ⁵² asserts that the health-care sector is recognized as an industry and many new life insurance entrants are providing health insurance benefits as riders. However, the general insurance companies issue health policies separately to the customers. The different marketing strategies adopted by the insurers for marketing health insurance policies are discussed and necessary suggestions are given for improving the marketing potential of these products. The concept and place of risk in the financial sector and the related managerial aspects are elaborately outlined in the book "Risk Management" by The Indian Institute of Banking and Finance, Mumbai. ⁵³, An overview of the risk management and its controlling techniques is also analyzed to enable the employees and practitioners of financial institutions to have a clear conception on risk management.

Rajeev Varghese ⁵⁴ asserts that group insurance is indeed a powerful tool which is beneficial not only to the members of the group but also to the group insurer and also the employer. He further adds that there is no wonder that the group insurance business has been steadily increasing.

Sathish ⁵⁵ in his article entitled "Life Insurance Marketing - A Phenomenon" contends that insurance marketing requires intriguing creativeness of the insurers implying updating knowledge on the markets with global perspective which calls for availability of enough right data or information at the hands of the operating offices.

Sridharan and Allimuthu ⁵⁶ assert that the Insurance Carriers and Banks in India managed to share the same vision as other Financial Conglomerates forming strategic partnerships known in all markets as bancassurance ventures. Bancassurance, the emerging distribution channel for the insurers, will have a large impact on the Indian financial services industry.

Veeraselvam ⁵⁷ foresees that Micro-insurance is meant for the low-income people. It is different from insurance in that it is a low-value product and requires different design and distribution strategies. Micro-insurance is insurance with low premiums and low caps/coverage. Micro insurance, like regular insurance, may be offered for a wide variety of risks.

Inderjit Singh ⁵⁸ analyze the different facets of the privatization of Indian Insurance Sector. The different approaches of managing risk based capital are discussed.

Chandra Sekhar ⁵⁹ observes that the Government has been pushing ahead with privatization despite there being no evidence of the nationalized insurance industry failing to meet its obligation to insurers or to the Government.

Chandarana Harish Kumar Muljibhai ⁶⁰ explains the different facets of the performance management of the LIC of India. The impact of liberalization and the entry of new insurers into the industry on the performance of the public sector insurer are also discussed elaborately in his thesis.

Desai Sneha Rupesh ⁶¹ feels that after the entry of private players into the insurance market, the Regulator has taken elaborate measures for developing insurance business in rural areas. The Regulator has also fixed targets to insurers with regard to rural business. However, the role played by the LIC in Rural Gujarat is not undermined.

Raj Kumar ⁶² expressed that the banking sector with its far and wider reach to the for an insurer to have a zero repudiation record and it may be essential to turn down a few claims that are otherwise wrongful as it impedes with the principle of equitability.

Ramesh ⁶³ argues that while it is desirable for an insurer to have a zero repudiation record and it may be essential to turn down a few claims that are otherwise wrongful as it impedes with the principle of equitability.

Sai Srinivas Dhulipala ⁶⁴ observes that the riders offer a host of benefits both to the insurer as well as to the insured and thus had come to be accepted as an integral component of life insurance business.

Saranghi Prakash Kumar ⁶⁵ addresses the importance of customer delight in the insurance industry and its role in the business registered by LIC. Further, the strategic implications of different problems and relevant suggestions are also discussed. Product innovation and availability of a variety of products of the LIC to suit the needs of the customers delighted them to some extent.

Narayanan ⁶⁶ felt that all insurers recognize the vast potential in the rural areas wherein a large percentage of our population lives. He states that rural market for insurance is a challenge to insurers. The existing marketing strategies are discussed and suitable marketing strategies for tapping insurance market in Coimbatore District are suggested.

Mrinalini Shah and Shweta Dixit ⁶⁷ conceptualize that the penetration of rural insurance in India requires a fresh approach to sell rural insurance products because of the limitations in insurance business. Since this activity revolves around agriculture, suitable insurance cover to the needs of the targeted rural customers has to be addressed.

Mishra and Mangala Bakshi ⁶⁸ have blended the modern day advancements in the field of insurance with conventional insurance knowledge and practice. This book has given a revised standard in the field of insurance academics, giving them a platform to build upon for posterity.

Shri Krishna Laxman Karve ⁶⁹ provides an understanding of the elementary principles of life insurance and their relevance to the present day insurance society. An in-depth analysis of the factors affecting measurement of risk and also the features of different life insurance products are given in the book. The process of salesmanship for enabling the prospective agent to imbibe the spirit and substance of the art of life insurance selling is also discussed.

A study conducted by **Rajesham and Rajender** ⁷⁰ revealed that insurance companies of India are required to come up with multi-benefit policies including tax benefits with quality based timely customer services and need to focus on health insurance which is one of the untapped areas of insurance including services through innovative products, smart marketing and aggressive distribution with internet facility with much individual attention transparency and flexibility to increase the quality and volume of insurance business. Today, the focus is on selling more products to existing customers to improve profitability, therefore customer – focused strategies require an effective CRM ensuring insurance firms monitor the ebb and flow of customer behaviour, giving them a holistic 360-degree view for their customers.

Phani Kumar ⁷¹ concentrates his emphasis mostly on the opinions and satisfaction of investors about life insurance on the basis of their socio-economic background.

Ram Pratap Sinha ⁷² emphasizes that in the Indian context, the Insurance Act, 1938 required all insurers to maintain sufficient assets at all times to meet the liabilities, thereby providing for a adequate solvency margin. But, the regulator, as a matter of prudence, has raised and prescribed a solvency margin of 150 per cent to be maintained at all points of time by the insurers.

Jagendra Kumar ⁷³ advocates that the CRM technology can help improve customer service and customer contact. More companies are moving towards supplying self-service to customers to replace face-to-face contact.

Gupta ⁷⁴ analyses the different aspects of insurance and also the related risk management components. The comparative cost-benefit analysis of insurance is also depicted.

Mushtaq Ahmed ⁷⁵ vividly discusses a comparative analysis of the strategies adopted by both LIC and private insurance players in selling insurance to the customers. Due to the intensity of competition faced by the LIC after liberalization, the Corporation has thought seriously of inculcating innovativeness in the strategies adopted for selling insurance products to the customers.

Narasimhan ⁷⁶ focuses on that his committee has suggested a somewhat differently worded addition to Sec.38 of the Insurance Act that would enable the IRDA to specify regulations - what type of assignment would be prohibited, restricted or otherwise regulated? - in the interests of policyholders or the general public.

Nageswara Rao and Madhavi ⁷⁷ observe that the insurance industry is facing a healthy competition which really benefits the public. The public sector LIC should further improve its product varieties and schemes to compete with the private sector and also change its attitude further towards service to survive in the market.

Mrinalini Shah and Shweta Dixit ⁷⁸ conceptualize that the penetration of rural insurance in India requires a fresh approach to sell rural insurance products because of the limitations in insurance business. Since this activity revolves around agriculture, suitable insurance cover to the needs of the targeted rural customers has to be addressed.

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The **Swarup Committee** ⁸⁰ recommendations for the insurance industry calling for the abolition of selling commissions borne by policy holders have made the players unhappy. The agents are worried that collecting money from policyholder would

prove difficult. The regulator and the insurance players have also voiced grievances against these recommendations.

Basavanhappa and Rajanalkar Laxman ⁸¹ show that the Private Insurance Companies have made their presence felt and over the years have achieved remarkable progress. There is a big opportunity to these companies in the Indian Life Insurance Sector. The companies have to bring out innovative products to suit the different requirements of the public. A healthy competition in the sector would be beneficial to both the players and also the public.

Krishna Swami ⁸² explains clearly the history of insurance, advantages of insurance and the role of insurance in the economy and also in the society. The life insurance products, the concepts of premium, investment management and solvency margin are also discussed at length in the book.

Murthy ⁸³ conclude that several changes have taken place since opening up of the insurance sector. After liberalization, insurance industry's outlook has been changed significantly. The number of private players and their innovative products are also made attractive for every social segment. The healthier competition has intensified to increase insurance density and penetration levels in order to fulfill customer needs.

Veeraselvam ⁸⁴ foresees that Micro-insurance is meant for the low-income people. It is different from insurance in that it is a low-value product and requires different design and distribution strategies. Micro-insurance is insurance with low premiums and low caps/coverage. Micro insurance, like regular insurance, may be offered for a wide variety of risks.

Inderjit Singh ⁸⁵ analyze the different facets of the privatization of Indian Insurance Sector. The different approaches of managing risk based capital are discussed.

Chandra Sekhar ⁸⁶ observes that the Government has been pushing ahead with privatization despite there being no evidence of the nationalized insurance industry failing to meet its obligation to insurers or to the Government. The LIC has not only put at the Government's disposal large volumes of capital for investment but also addressed the problems of insurance for the poor.

According to **Rajendran and Natarajan** ⁸⁷, in this Indian context, insurance habit among the general public during the independence decade was quite rare and in the following decades, it increased slowly. There was a remarkable improvement in the Indian insurance industry soon after the acceptance and adaptation of liberalization, privatization, and globalization (LPG) in the year 1991. After 1991, the Indian life insurance industry has geared up in all respects, as well as it being forced to face a lot of healthy competition from many national as well as international private insurance players. The fall in the savings rate and increased competition in the primary market and particularly the aggressive mobilization by the mutual fund posed serious challenges to LIC.

Pooja Bhalla and Gagandeep Kaur ⁸⁸ present that the opening up of the insurance sector to private players has posed a challenge to the public sector giant i.e. LIC of India. Though, it still enjoys the dominant position but the proportionate share is decreasing year after year. On the other hand, the private players with their innovative products, smart marketing, wider distribution networks and better customer service have been successful in attracting a large number of customers.

Justin Paul and Padmatha Suresh ⁸⁹ elucidate in detail the concept, benefits and tax concessions of insurance. The waves of globalization and liberalization and their impact on insurance industry are also analysed vividly in the book.

Nalini Prava Tripathy and Prabir Pal ⁹⁰ provide an insight into the operational policies, practices and issues relating to the insurance business with the ever-changing and latest trends in the sector. It also provides for the current stage of development of the insurance industry and future prospects of industry in our country for a better tomorrow.

Srujan ⁹¹ presented an insurer's financial situations with respect to future unstable economic conditions. An attempt is made to study the potential utilities of the process of dynamic financial analysis to the insurer in a real situation.

Harsh Arora ⁹² opines that to get good insurance business, long-term customer relationship is necessary and it should possess certain ethical aspects. These aspects are to be considered in the training given to their agents and frontline managers by the potential companies to hone the company's objective of getting the maximum market share in the near future.

Kanan ⁹³ writes that due to the very nature of insurance business, it is impossible to guarantee solvency with certainty. He further adds that in order to come to a practicable definition, it is necessary to make clear under which circumstances the appropriateness of the Assets to cover claims is to be considered.

Jagendra Kumar ⁹⁴ mentions that the LIC settles a large number of death claims every year, yet it is compelled to repudiate death claims in case where full disclosures of material information at the time of taking the policy was not made.

Hari Govind Mishra ⁹⁵ felt that the Branch Manager has dual responsibilities to perform both marketing and administrative functions of the Branch. He is instrumental in developing cordial relations with customers by reducing the number of complaints and also expediting claims procedure.

Gupta Ajit Kumar ⁹⁶ highlights the different facets of the investment management of the LIC of India in the Cooperative and Private Sectors within the broader regulatory framework of the IRDA. A comparative analysis of the management practices of the LIC of India relating to funds is discussed and that between the two sectors, the investments in private sector are attracting more returns than co-operative sector in many cases of study.

Srinivasan ⁹⁷ categorically states that the different features of insurance contracts and also the principles of insurance law are very much relevant for study to the insurers and their people in understanding insurance contracts. The maxims applicable

Sandeep Batra ⁹⁸ mentions that the insurance game has barely begun in India. The insurance market is still growing at 17 per cent, with the private companies growing at 3-4 times more that rate. In the present scenario, more and more Chartered Accountants are joining this sector in various capacities.

Sharma Rajendra Prasad ⁹⁹ observed that there is much innovativeness in the marketing strategies adopted by the private insurance players. The private insurance players are mostly technology-driven and hence they are on the forefront in the area of introducing on-line and mobile marketing strategies.

Shiva Belavadi ¹⁰⁰ asserts that the golden key for success of a life insurer is the deliverance of the promise. Delivering the promise is indeed that moment of truth, a

culmination of the cycle which completes the obligations placed upon the insurer in the insurance process timely and promptly.

Sandeep Joshi and Manmeet Singh Rai ¹⁰¹ referred to the various facets of the concept of insurable interest and advocate that insurable interest is the main realm of an insurance contract and its absence renders insurance policy void and also meaningless and advocate that insurable interest is the main realm of an insurance contract and its absence renders insurance policy void and also meaningless.

Neelam C. Gulati ¹⁰² project an insight into the basics of insurance, types of insurance, claims management, role of technology in the insurance sector and also the history and future expectations of Indian life insurance industry.

John .Hull ¹⁰³ explains in detail the various aspects of risk management in different companies. The important derivative factors are discussed with reference to risk business along with necessary illustrative examples.

Chauhan Monica ¹⁰⁴ states that the insurance industry is mostly a customer-oriented industry and customers are demanding more and more of innovative insurance products to fulfill their needs and obligations. The important factors affecting the selection of life insurance products are identified by the researcher and these are the product characteristics, terms of premium payment, duration of the policy, number of switch-offs in the solution, risk coverage and return on the policies.

Sanjeev Kumar ¹⁰⁵ states that investment operations are crucial to the business of the LIC. The Corporation, over a long period of time, has built up a large corpus of fund. LIC of India has required investing the funds to the best advantage of the investors keeping in view the national priorities. But, during its long-regime and in many cases, a part of the Life fund has been invested by the Corporation in securities has been yielding very low returns for satisfying the regulatory conditions.

Jha ¹⁰⁶ has gone through the various components and aspects of insurance marketing. The motive of this is to sensitize the instrumentality of marketing in promoting the insurance business in India.

Nageswa Rao, ¹⁰⁷ elucidated clearly the impact of the deregulation process of the Government on the Banking and Insurance organizations. The Challenges so accompanying this deregulation and also suitable remedial measures are discussed.

Jaya Prakash Rai ¹⁰⁸ conducted an empirical study to know the attitude and behavioural patterns of the selected insurance customers of the District. He suggests that customer expectations towards different attitudinal factors are to be properly analyzed to formulate a suitable and a necessary marketing strategy for each and every insurer.

Tripti Dhote ¹⁰⁹ highlights the current trend in insurance advertising. It focuses on the effective advertising strategy of various insurance companies which attracted not only the customer but also even the biggest of the corporate making insurance a prosperous proposition to sell.

Anand Bansal ¹¹⁰ concludes that the outcome of privatization process over a period of time has been proved positive and identified as the beginning of new era with many heights to achieve. But there is an urgent need to adopt professionalized approach for the bright future of the industry.

Krishanaveni ¹¹¹ highlights the fact that detailed standards should be issued by the Regulator covering the constitution and also the methods of calculating reserves and provisions to ensure that all companies have to follow and adopt policies of capital adequacy standards in time and in tune with the best of the international practices. She

also asserts that an Insurance Information Bureau should be created with data on underwriting policies, incidents of loss, claims and insurance brand.

Radha Krishna ¹¹² finds that the Tata AIG has come up with a multi-channel distribution strategy i.e. leveraging bancassurance and corporate agents in addition to advisors and financial service consultants. This strategy had saved the distribution costs and helped in increasing the customer product offerings in a significant measure.

Awasthi, ¹¹³ is of the opinion that the lack of proper explanation of the terms of insurance contracts and misconceptions about their nature as fixed income investments are leading reasons for consumer grievances. Such misconception needs to be eliminated urgently by the insurers and the Regulator has to take initiative in this regard by formulating and implementing suitable regulations.

Murthy, ¹¹⁴ states that the proposed increase in the FDI Cap from 26 to 49 per cent has got a very good potential to have a competitive edge over other organizations and there is an urgent need to infuse huge amount of capital into insurance by the foreign insurance collaborators.

Ravishankar, ¹¹⁵ argues that in a changing business environment where returns are critical, insurance companies should consider several options while investing their funds. The role of the regulator has to be to only caution the insurance companies by prescribing capital adequacy norms and not to refrain from investing in the most profitable assets.

Suri Seeta Ram ¹¹⁶ describes clearly his personal growth as an insurance agent while thanking his mentors for honing professional skills. Two basic lessons that almost all the agents are coerced into learning are 'Rebate' and 'Wrong Medicals'. These are lessons that are very hard to unlearn. He emphasizes that the purpose of life insurance is not just tax relief and savings, but a lot more to think and learn.

An analysis of the above mentioned literature indicates that most of the studies were understood to be confined mainly to an opinion poll on insurance awareness and marketing strategies of insurance products. Further, these studies assessed the performance of the insurance sector from a particular and a very specific dimension. No comprehensive study seems to have been undertaken so far to evaluate the performance of public and private sector insurance players in all respects. It is also hoped that the data presented, the observations made and conclusions arrived at in these studies will be useful for inter-sectoral comparison, not only in the case of other players who newly entered and those who are proposed to enter in the years to come in the insurance sector.

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